

BUYING BEHAVIOUR AND SATISFACTION OF CONSUMERS IN RELATION TO D-MART

Dr. Sapna Sharma

Assistant. Professor

St.Thomas College Bhilai

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Abstract: D-Mart is a chain of hyper markets and supermarkets in by R.K. Damani .A consumer buying behaviour with reference to D-Mart is for checking the buying behavior of an individual consumer when he did shopping at D-Mart. The study was carried as per the steps of Marketing Research D-Mart's vision is to make available products categories for the customers everyday use at the 'best' value.

Keywords: Buying Behaviour, Customer.

1. INTRODUCTION

D-Mart was started by Mr.Radhakishan Damani to address the growing needs of the Indian family.. The mission is to be the lowest priced retailer in the regions they operate; their business continues to grow with new locations planned in more cities. It was founded on 15th May 2002. As of March 2025, D-Mart has a total of 415 stores across 12 states and union territories in India. The retail chain has significantly expanded its presence since its first store opened in 2002. As of July 2025 D-Mart has a market cap of **₹2.781 Trillion**. This makes D-Mart the world's 675th most valuable company according to our data.. There is a D- Mart in Bhilai Sector 9, and another in Bhilai 3 near Old Sairam Ford Showroom and G E Road. D-Mart seeks to provide one-stop shopping experience for the entire family, meeting all their daily household needs A wide selection of home utility products is offered, including foods ,toiletries ,beauty products, garments ,kitchenware ,bed and bath linen, and much more .

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

One of the important steps in the planning of any research study is a careful review of the research journals, books, dissertations, these and other sources of information on the problem to be investigated. It enables the researcher to define the limits of his field and to avoid unfruitful and useless problem areas.

STUDIES RELATED TO RESEARCH ON A CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR WITH REFERENCE TO D-MART

(Mazursky and Jacoby 1986); and others seeking to conduct a meta-analysis of retail patronage studies (Pan & Zinkhan 2006). However, the exciting literature did not retail image Consumers perception of store image is based, in part, on functional Qualities that the store may possess.

Lindquist analyzed over 20 studies dealing with store image formation and identified 35 different aspects that reveal in prior studies where clustering techniques had been used to study consumer's perception of influence store image formation..

A later study by Baker, Grewal and Voss (2002) also confirmed that service quality was a key determinant of store image. Given the prevalence in the literature of merchandise and service as two key determinations in the formation of store image.

OBJECTIVE

- To study the satisfaction level of consumers towards D- Mart.
- To study the factors influencing purchasing behavior with respect to D-Mart.
- To find out whether the product of D-Mart is affordable for everyone or not.
- To study which type of product is more in demand.
- To study about the offers of D-mart as compared to other stores.
- To study the availability of variety of products.
- To study how frequently people prefer D-Mart.
- To find out the level of shopping from D-mart.
- To study the quality of product.

LIMITATIONS

This research is conducted on a sample size, so it might be possible that the information given by such respondents may not match with the reply of total customer available in the D-Mart that time.

- The study was restricted to only the customers of D-Mart. The time constrain was an irritating factor, as more time was required to carry out study on other aspects of the topic.
- The result & analysis is based on the customer survey method & small sample size has taken only 50.
- Findings are related to areas.
- It might be possible that the answers given by the respondents are of biasness,

Since the study is on retail sector first the detail study of the store has been conducted about its management team its structure the number of departments which all brands do the store has, who are the suppliers about its warehouses. Based on the topic objectives were set and to arrive at the opinion on objectives a set of 50 Questionnaires were designed and response is collected from the customers who are visiting the store. For data collection personal investigation, filed survey, as well as sampling method are adopted. For this project the area of research is Bhilai.

Data Collection

For this research the area of research is Bhilai.

Well-structured questionnaires were prepared & the survey was undertaken. Feedback for the display has been taken by asking questions & observations have also done to gather primary information. There is also a use of secondary data, collected from the various journals, books, & websites & from store managers.

Primary Data: Field Survey

Secondary Data–Mart records(Company websites) Area of research: Bhilai

Research approach: Survey method

Methods of Collecting Primary Data: Primary data are collected by the following methods:

3. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The project aims to study a consumer buying behaviours with reference to D-Mart implemented by many numbers of consumers in Bhilai city. To evaluate the effectiveness of this program in Bhilai city, as questionnaire was prepared for finding out the Actual consumer who shops from D-Mart as well as any small Store or Superstore. This questionnaire was distributed among a sample of 50 Consumers who shops from D-mart & others in a particular area of Bhilai city. The results obtained from the responses were analyzed.

Analysis of responses.**1.GENDER**

Gender	No.of responses	Percentage
Male	18	36
Female	32	64
Total	50	100

Percentage

- Male
- Female
- Total

Analysis

From the survey it is analyze that 36% are male and 64% are female.

Interpretation

It is observed that females are attracted more towards D-mart.

2. The Respondents were asked which store they prefer first.

Store	No.of responses	Percentage
D-mart	30	60
OtherStore	12	24
Both	8	16
None	0	0
Total	50	100

Percentage

- D-mart
- OtherStore
- Both
- None
- Total

Analysis:

From the survey, from 50 respondents, 30 gave response for more powerful preference to D-Mart is 60%, Other Store 24%, both 16% & none 0%.

Interpretation:

Majority of the customers are given response for most powerful preference is D-Mart. We can also interpret that the D-Mart comparison is more powerful attract with the purchasing systems by the D- Mart.

3. The Respondents were asked how frequently they Visit D-Mart.

Visits	No.of responses	Percentage
Daily	1	2
Weekly	17	34
Monthly	30	60
Yearly	2	4
Total	50	100

Percentage

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Yearly
- Total

Analysis

From the above analysis it is observed that:

- Only 1 consumer can prefer D-Mart for daily shopping purpose. 17 number of consumers can prefer D-Mart for weekly shopping purpose.
- 30 number of consumers can prefer D-Mart for monthly shopping purpose.
- Lastly 2 number of consumers can prefer D-Mart for yearly shopping purpose.

Interpretation

Majority of consumers like D-Mart for monthly shopping purpose. D-Mart offers the various numbers of offers with affordable prices which are easily preferable for every individual in any income group.

4. The Respondents were asked about level of shopping they do.

Level of Shopping	No. of responses	Percentage
Below 1000	10	20
Below 3000	11	22
Below 5000	20	40
More than 5000	9	18
Total	50	100

Below 1000	20
Below 3000	22
Below 5000	40
More than 5000	18

Analysis:

From the above analysis it is observed that:

- 10 number of Consumers level of Shopping from D-Mart 20% for the shopping of a product at the below 1000 price list.
- While 11 number of consumers level of shopping from D-Mart 22% for the shopping of products at the below 3000 price list.
- While 20 number of consumers level of shopping from D-Mart 40% for the shopping of products at the below 5000 price list.
- Only 9 number of consumers level of shopping is more than 5000.

Interpretation:

So from this analysis it is observed that at present in the Bhilai city D-Mart shopping mall is affordable for the middle income group. It is not suitable for every income group.

5. The Respondents were asked about type of product they prefer most.

Type of Product	No. of responses	Percentage
Grocery	04	8
Clothes	06	12
Household	28	56
Food items	12	24
Total	50	100

Grocery	8
Clothes	12
Household	56
Food items	24

Analysis:

From the survey of 50 respondent,8% prefer D-Mart for Grocery items,12% prefer D-Mart for clothes,56% prefer D-Mart for household and 24% prefer D-Mart for food items.

Interpretation:

Majority of customers are given response for household items of the store like the most. We are also interpreting that some of the product's brand are predecided in advance and for some of the products customers not pre decide any brand. As per household items are concerned customers pre decide the brand as many branded products are available in the store and some people are *don't* like purchase grocery from the store.

6. The Respondents were asked about their Ratings for return policy of D-Mart.

Return Policy Rating	No.of responses	Percentage
Excellent	20	40
Good	16	32
Satisfactory	14	28
Not-Satisfactory	0	0
Total	50	100

Percentage

A pie chart titled 'Percentage' showing the distribution of return policy ratings. The chart is divided into four segments: a large blue segment for 'Excellent' (40%), a red segment for 'Good' (32%), a green segment for 'Satisfactory' (28%), and a very small segment for 'Not-Satisfactory' (0%). A legend to the right of the chart identifies the colors: blue for Excellent, red for Good, and green for Satisfactory.

Analysis:

- 20 consumers give Excellent responses in very huge percentage is 40% for returns policy of D-Mar
- 16 consumers give good responses in 32% to the returns policy of D -Mart.
- 14fconsumers give satisfactory response in 28% to the returns policy.

Interpretation

Lastly no one consumer says that with the D-Mart policy they are not satisfied.

Zero number of consumers are not satisfied with the returns policy.

7. The Respondents were asked D-Mart is affordable or not.

Affordable	No .of responses	Percentage
Yes	45	90
No	5	10
Total	50	100

Percentage

A pie chart titled 'Percentage' showing the distribution of responses regarding D-Mart's affordability. The chart is divided into three segments: a large blue segment for 'Yes' (90%), a small red segment for 'No' (10%), and a green segment for 'Total' (100%). A legend to the right of the chart identifies the colors: blue for Yes, red for No, and green for Total.

Analysis

- From the survey, of 50respondents it is observed that 45 numbers of consumers responded in large percentage i.e. 90% said it to be affordable.
- There after 5 consumers responded that it is unaffordable.(10% of respondents)

- Interpretation

Majority of consumers thought that D-mart is affordable to everyone. It is highly preferable for everyone.

Findings

- Most of the customers by their requirement in D-mart & any other Super store or small store on daily basis only. Customers retailed that D -Mart & any Stores provide qualitative products & services with reasonable price.
- At present D-mart &any other Super store or small stores provide different types of products assortments to the customers.
- D-Mart is hypermarket as it provides various kinds of goods like apparels, grocery, stationery, food items, electronic items, leather items, crockery, decorative items, sport items, chocolates and many more. It competes with all the specialty
- Stores of different products which provide goods at a discounted rate all through the year. We never need to go for a particular store where only one item is available.
- D-Mart mainly deals with middle income group people who want qualitative product with reasonable cost.
- There are 234 stores of D-Mart in different cities in India. It seems that there is a vast growth of D-Mart lying as customers demand is increasing for D-Mart as compare to stores

After analyzing the data and successfully testing the methods the researcher would like to make following suggestions in context of a consumer buying behaviour with reference to D-Mart in Bhilai city.

- D-Mart should provide large parking places for customers as compared to other stores. So, they can easily park their vehicles.
- The infrastructure is needed to be changed to a bit during weekends as heavy crowd comes in D-Mart during those days.
- D-mart should include more of branded products its product category as compared to stores. So as to attract the brand choosy people to come into D- Mart.
- D-Mart should keep offers to attract customers in regular intervals so that there should not belong term gap, because offer is the most influencing factor which is responsible for customer purchase decision.
- They also concentrate on hoardings advertisements they should show ads and promotional offers at a regular interval in languages like Hindi & English.
- Hoardings should be placed in uncovered area.
- Separate billing counter should be provided for shoppers purchasing, few products for faster customer turnover.
- The staff is not well trained to handle customers belonging to different backgrounds and attitudes, so better selection and training programs should be initiated.

4. CONCLUSION

D-Mart is a hypermarket as it provides various kinds of goods like apparels, grocery, stationary, food items, electronic items, leather items, crockery, decorative items, sport items, chocolates and many more. It competes with all the specialty stores of different products which provide goods at a discounted rate all throughout the year. It seems that there is a vast growth of D- Mart as customers demand is increasing for D-Mart. It has emerged as a hub of shopping specially for middle class people.

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